

Speculation on Describing All Uniform Motion by the Same Constant

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It is well known that uniform classical motion may be described by a constant velocity i.e. one which does not change in time. A different constant number, however, is needed for each velocity so uniform motion in general is not being represented by a single number in this scenario. In (1) we noted how a single number such as energy E could represent systems linked to different physical theories. For example, a classical particle may move according to $\frac{1}{2}mv^2 + V(x) = E$ where v is velocity. On the one hand a single number E describes each point (x,t) , but at each point there is different detailed motion such as potential energy, velocity etc. Similarly in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas $\exp(-(\frac{1}{2}mv^2 + V(x))/T)$ is proportional to probability. For a given $E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 + V(x)$ there are many v,x points which have the same E and thus probability. Finally for a quantum bound state there is a single E_n (energy) even though there is a potential energy $V(x)$ and average kinetic energy $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} / W$ (W =wavefunction) at each x .

In this note we ask whether a single number may apply to all uniform motion with this constant being equal then to different details in each system. The reason we ask this question is that we think a given constant velocity, say 25 m/s, does not characterize uniform motion. The problem we argue is one of resolution of x and t . For example, 25 m/s may characterize very erratic motion from $x=0$ to $x=25$ m in a period of 1 sec. This simply means the average speed is 25 m/s, not that the motion is uniform. To bypass this argument one may suggest perfect x, t resolution for all speeds. In such a case erratic motion may only exist in an extremely tiny dx or dt which approaches 0. This suggests there exists a spacetime (x,t) which may analyze all uniform motion with infinitesimal precision i.e. is all-seeing. It is not clear that there exists any physical mechanism for this.

We argue instead that velocity is a property of a moving object, not of spacetime. An object undergoes force over distance and receives a velocity which is one of its properties. In such a case infinitesimal resolution of t and x may not apply to all velocities. In fact if v velocity is a property of the object, x,t resolution may also be associated properties. Thus details of a particular uniform motion are not simply v (which yields p and $E=pp/2m$ nonrelativistically), but also x and t resolution. Is it possible that these details may combine to create a single constant representing all uniform motion? We argue that this is possible and that this constant is in fact the free particle action $-Et+px$ which holds both relativistically and nonrelativistically. For t proportional to $1/E$ and p proportional to $1/x$ (same proportionality constant) one has a single constant, Action=0, describing all uniform motion. We however, arrive at the form $-Et+px$ without using notions of action or Lagrangian.

Constant Values and Loss of Information

In (1) we noted that a classical particle may move according to $\frac{1}{2}mv^2 + V(x) = E$. A single number E characterizes each x,t point. Given E one has no idea at which x,t point the particle may be found. Thus many different points x,t with different physical properties (e.g. different speed, momentum, kinetic energy, potential energy) all map to the same E i.e. are equivalent in a sense. We argued that this is linked to time reversal symmetry and also may be applied to a

Maxwell-Boltzmann gas i.e. $\exp(-.5mv^2 + V(x))$ such that $E_1 = .5mv^2 + V(x)$ means many x points map to the same E_1 and same probability. Furthermore it may be linked to a quantum bound state which has a single constant E_n linked to all x points as well. Thus there are many detail points which all map to the same constant.

We ask: Can one have all uniform motion i.e. all constant velocity scenarios map into a single number? Certainly each speed is constant i.e not dependent on time, but this is not a single constant. We argue that this single number suggests that each scenario represents uniform motion. One might argue that a constant speed already suggests this point, but we argue that this depends on resolution of x and t . We suggest it is an assumption to think that spacetime (x,t) may resolve all uniform motion in the same way with equal infinitesimal resolution.

X,t Resolution and Uniform Motion

Consider a speed of 25 m/s. One may immediately ask: What are the resolutions of x and t ? For example, one may interpret this number as meaning that on average a particle covers a distance of 25 m in 1 sec. There are many different kinds of motions with accelerations i.e nonuniform scenarios which may satisfy this description. Thus simply stating 25 m/s does not necessarily mean uniform motion. To bypass this issue one may argue that there is infinitesimally fine resolution of x and t for all velocities. Then erratic motion is restricted to tiny dx and dt regions and these tend to zero. This, however, suggests that it is spacetime that somehow determines velocity, i.e. is all-seeing with no physical mechanism given for this, rather than have velocity (energy, momentum) and possibly resolution be a property of a particle. A particle at rest receives a velocity by being acted on by a force and this velocity is associated with a momentum and a kinetic energy. We argue that there is no reason to assume that spacetime resolves x and t with infinitesimal precision. Rather, even at a classical level, resolution of x and t may be properties like energy, momentum and v . In other words particles with different speeds may have different x , t resolutions. Given that ct and x are both lengths one might consider trying to treat them on the same footing.

Consider two results from Newtonian mechanics:

$$\text{Impulse} = \int F dt = \Delta p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \int F dx = \Delta \text{Kinetic energy} \quad ((1b))$$

where F is force and p momentum.

Thus if one treats t and x in a "kind" of equal manner one might consider the two terms:

$$\int F dt x = p x \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \int F dx t = E t \quad \text{where } E = p^2/2m \quad ((2b))$$

Now $v = \text{velocity} = x/t$ so x and t are not exactly on the same footing. Rather one may take:

$$p x - E t = A \quad \text{and consider } dx/dt = E/p \quad ((3))$$

This happens to be the result for light which is fine because it also has energy, momentum and space and time resolution. In fact, one may see that $px-Et$ is the classical action for a particle with rest mass in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases if one takes $v=x/t$ i.e.

$$\text{Action} = .5m v^2 t \text{ (nonrelativistic)} \quad \text{Action} = - m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \text{ relativistic} \quad ((4))$$

If one wishes to have a single number represent all uniform motion such that this number is equal to an expression describing details then one may take:

$$x= b/p \quad \text{and} \quad t = b/E \quad \text{where } b \text{ is a constant in } A= -Et+px \quad ((5))$$

Thus time and space resolution are defined up to the constant b (which is taken to be $\hbar$ in the literature). $\text{Action}=0$ represents all uniform motion such that given this number it may apply to any speed. This means, however, that one must have different space and time resolutions for each speed. In addition, trying to treat x and t on equal footing leads to different time and space resolutions for a single speed.

Thus we argue that a constant speed number is not enough to imply uniform motion because this number is associated with its own space and time resolution. These resolutions must be manifested physically in space. For example, there must be a physical manifestation of a wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and in fact this appears in 1 slit, 2 slit etc experiments of an electron etc and in bound state wavefunctions. It seems, however, that this wavelength is easily manifested in certain speed and length ranges, but is incredibly small in the usual classical speed and length ranges and so goes unnoticed. Nevertheless the argument of space time (x,t) resolving infinitesimal time and space resolutions is an assumption that need not be true even at the classical level. Different so-called uniform motions actually have different resolutions and so are not really uniform in a sense. In quantum mechanics two shifted distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are taken as an ordered pair so that their modulus $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx)$ is a constant i.e. describes uniform motion even though there are clearly crests and troughs present. We argue that a different way to represent all uniform motion is to have it be represented by a constant number, namely 0, which in turn is equal to an expression yielding details of each uniform speed member namely $-Et+px$. (This is similar to E representing each x,t point for a classical particle, but $.5mv^2+V(x)$ yielding details. A given E maps to many x,t points just as $A=0$ maps to all uniform speed scenarios.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that given a uniform speed number say 25 m/s, this is not enough to characterize that the motion is uniform. One needs to know the space x and time t resolution. For example, if the particle simply covers 25 m on average in 1 sec, many erratic motions are possible with much acceleration. In order to bypass this issue, one must assume infinitesimal resolution of x and t by spacetime and it is not clear that there is any physical mechanism to achieve this. Rather we assume that velocity (momentum, energy) are properties of a particle which it acquires by being acted on by a force. Thus x and t resolution may be part of these

properties. In other words different speeds may have different x and t resolutions because these are part of the particle motion and not based on an “all-seeing” spacetime. If this is the case, one might argue that a single number should describe all uniform motion such that this number is equivalent to the details of each uniform velocity. This is similar to a single number E describing each (x,t) point in the classical motion: $E = .5mv^2 + V(x)$.

Given that x and ct appear to be on the same footing except for the fact that $v=x/t$ one may try using the Newtonian mechanics expressions $\int F dt = \Delta(p)$ and $\int F dx = \Delta(KE)$. This leads to two terms: $\int F dt x = p x$ and $\int F dx t = KE t$ or Et . Taking account of x/t by inserting a minus yields $A = -Et + px$ so that $dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx$ which yields a solution for light. Given $A=0$, one would require a time resolution of b/E and a space one of b/p . Thus one number, $A=0$, may categorize all uniform motion with time and spatial resolution being details of each speed scenario and not a property of an all-seeing spacetime. These arguments are classical, but lead to the idea of quantum wavelength and frequency we argue.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Constant Energy, Lack of Information Equilibrium and Time Reversal (preprint, zenodo, 2022)